

OS Awards

European Public Recognition Scheme for Open Source SW/HW Initiatives

First / Intermediate Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan 2 *Project deliverable D7.2*

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This deliverable provides a report on the dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan for the OS Awards.EU project. It is the second of a series laying out the plan and reports on the implementation of activities carried out until M18

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/ Acronym	Definition
Academy	European Open Source Academy
AV	Audio-visual
Awards	European Open Source Awards
DG CNECT	Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
MC	Master of the Ceremony
MEP	Member of the European Parliament
OC	Organising Committee of the European Open Source Awards
OFE	OpenForum Europe
OS	Open source
OS Awards.EU	EU-funded project, OS Awards.EU, Grant agreement ID: 101189668
PC	Programme Committee of the European Open Source Awards
RISE	Research Institutes of Sweden
Tecnia	Fundacion Tecnia Research & Innovation
Trust-IT	Trust-IT Services

About OS Awards.EU

OS Awards.EU is a 30-month initiative dedicated to establishing an European Open Source Academy and a prominent European Public Recognition Scheme for Open Source Software (OS SW) and Hardware (HW). By creating the annual European Open Source Awards, guided by the expert European Open Source Academy, the project will celebrate outstanding contributions and foster greater interest, integration, utilisation, and exploitation of OS assets across Europe.

Strategically leveraging the EU Open Source Week alongside key European events, the project will amplify the awards' profile and engage the community. The European OS Academy, in collaboration with the European Commission, will ensure award legitimacy and drive open source skills development. By intertwining recognition, legitimacy, and community engagement, OS Awards.EU aims to cultivate a comprehensive strategy that drives innovation, advances open source technologies, enhances EU competitiveness, and strengthens its open strategic autonomy.

OS Awards.eu partners

The **OS Awards.eu** consortium consists of 7 partners from six different European countries:

1. RISE RESEARCH INSTITUTES OF SWEDEN AB (RISE), Sweden
2. OPENFORUM EUROPE (OFE), Belgium
3. FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION (TECNALIA), Spain
4. TRUST-IT SERVICES SRL (Trust-IT), Italy
5. BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION (BSC CNS), Spain
6. ASSOCIATION PROFESSIONNELLE EUROPEENNE DU LOGICIEL LIBRE (APELL asbl), Belgium
7. FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN, Germany

Table of Contents

1	Introduction and scope	9
1.1	Stakeholder and targeted KERs	9
2	Communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement plan and interim report	11
2.1	Brand identities	11
2.2	Channels Overview	11
2.2.1	Website.....	11
2.2.2	OS Awards.EU-Driven Events	22
2.2.3	Events – Third-Party.....	23
2.2.4	Email outreach, newsletters and the EOSA Magazine	25
2.2.5	Press and Media	25
2.3	Campaigns	29
2.3.1	Campaign 1: Branding and Awareness & Recurring Activities	30
2.3.2	Campaign 2: Academy Awareness & Promotion	30
2.3.3	Campaign 3: Flagship Event Promotion and Recruitment	32
2.3.4	Campaign 4: OS Synergies.....	34
3	Exploitation Plan	37
3.1	Exploitation Planning.....	37
3.1.1	KER 1 (Academy and Awards): European Open Source Academy and Awards Framework.....	37
3.1.2	KER 2 (Skills Strategy): Strategy for OS Skills Development.....	39
3.1.3	KER 3 (OS Thought-Leadership): Thought-Leadership Outputs and Tools.....	40
4.	Conclusions.....	41
Appendix I.	Handbook	42
Appendix II.	Media Press Clippings	44

Table of Figures

Figure 1 Logos of EOSA & the Awards	11
Figure 2 Timeline of the Website Releases 2025-2027	11
Figure 3 Visual Mock-up approved for the new EOSA homepage	12
Figure 4 Academy members section (left) & dedicated page for an Academy Member (right)	13
Figure 5 Press Releases section (left) and Academy in the press (right) website sections	14
Figure 6 EOSA Policy section	15
Figure 7 Data Visualisation Tool “homepage” (left), Blogspot (center) and Interactive graphic (right)	16
Figure 8 List of Preliminary Materials identified to be made available in the online catalogue	17
Figure 9 Snapshot of European OS Awards website in 2026	17
Figure 10 EOSA LinkedIn Snapshot	19
Figure 11 EOSA Mastodon snapshot	20
Figure 12 EOSA Bluesky snapshot	20
Figure 13 EOSA YouTube snapshot	21
Figure 14 Landing page of OS Awards.EU ZENODO Community	21
Figure 15 Example of a presentation image of a EOSA Masterclass	22
Figure 16 Cover of 1st EOSA Magazine	25
Figure 17 Snapshot of a PR focused on European OS Awards 2026	26
Figure 18 Distribution of Articles by Media Sector (left) and Distribution of Articles by Media Type (right)	27
Figure 19 List of media coverage with monthly visit metrics	27
Figure 20 Example of article (part1)	28
Figure 21 Example of article (part2)	28
Figure 22 "Academy in Press" section on EOSA website	29
Figure 23 EOSA promotional video screenshot	32
Figure 24 Testimonial video screenshot	33

Table of Tables

Table 1 Overview of OS Awards.eu KERs and stakeholders	10
Table 2 Overview of EOSA events organised and planned ones.....	23
Table 3 EOSA presence at third-party events.....	24
Table 4 Overview of Campaign 1 KIPs between M1-M20.....	30
Table 5 Overview of Campaign 2 KIPs between M1-M20.....	31
Table 6 Table 7 Overview of Campaign 3 KIPs.....	32
Table 8 Overview of Campaign 3 KIPs between M1-M18.....	33
Table 9 External contributors for EOSA Magazine	35
Table 10 Overview of Campaign 4 KIPs between M1-M18.....	35
Table 11 Overview of EOSA established synergies by M18	36
Table 12 KER 1 Exploitation Planning	38
Table 13 KER 2 Exploitation Planning.....	39
Table 14 KER 3 Exploitation Planning.....	40

Executive Summary

This document represents the second in a series of three iterations of the OS Awards.EU dissemination, exploitation and communication plan. Like its predecessor, D7.1, it also serves as the communication plan for the European Open Source Academy (EOSA).

The primary objective of WP7 is to promote and disseminate the project’s ambitions, ongoing activities and key exploitable results (KERs) to strategic stakeholder groups. This is achieved through content-rich communication campaigns and impactful engagement with media representatives, aiming to expand the visibility and recognition of both EOSA and OS Awards beyond their core audiences. During this reporting period, multiple integrated communication tools were implemented and refined, maintaining strong coordination across all Work Packages.

This document, entitled “D7.2 First / Intermediate Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan,” outlines the results and impact of dissemination and communication activities carried out between May 2025 (M7) and April 2026 (M18). These efforts focused not only on increasing engagement with media channels, but also on enhancing the visibility of preliminary KER results. This was supported by the launch of new sections on the EOSA website and a redesigned OS Awards.eu online space. The document also includes a preliminary overview of strategies for the sustainability and exploitation of project KERs beyond the project’s duration.

This report will be followed by a third and final iteration, “D8.1 Final Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Report,” scheduled for April 2027 (M30). This final report will provide a comprehensive overview of OS Awards.eu KERs from a communication and dissemination perspective, along with a finalised definition of their exploitation strategies.

The document is structured into the following sections, outlining the results achieved during this reporting period:

- Section 1 provides an overview of OS Awards.eu stakeholders and identifies the KERs most relevant to each group;
- Section 2 presents the communication and dissemination activities carried out in recent months. It is structured around branding, communication channels, and specific campaigns, in alignment with the framework introduced in D7.1;
- Section 3 offers a preliminary overview of the exploitation measures related to OS Awards.eu results;
- Section 4 concludes the document and is followed by two appendices, which include detailed information on press clippings and the Handbook on Communications and Outreach.

1 Introduction and scope

This document “D7.2 First/Intermediate Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan” reports on the dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities carried out during the first half of the OS Awards.eu project. It benchmarks progress against the expected KPIs while providing an overview of planned activities for the remaining project period. The activities described were implemented in accordance with the original plan set out in D7.1, incorporating feedback received from the review report in May 2025 and reflecting the current state of the Open Source sector, a constantly evolving and dynamic landscape.

As with D7.1, this report provides inputs regarding two main groups of topics. Firstly, it provides a detailed overview of stakeholder engagement conducted during the first 18 months of the project, complemented with distinct yet complementary communication and dissemination channels, including updates on the campaigns currently in place. Secondly, an overview of preliminary achievements and forward-looking planning regarding the OS Awards.eu Exploitation Plan, which will reach its climax in the following reporting period and will be detailed in the next iteration of this report.

1.1 Stakeholder and targeted KERs

The success and sustainability of the OS Awards.eu project depends not only on the quality of its outputs and initiatives, but also on how effectively these results are aligned with the needs and expectations of diverse stakeholder groups. OS Awards.eu must ensure its outcomes are relevant, accessible and actionable for a wide spectrum of actors, from open source developers and academic researchers to policy makers, industry and civil society.

Each stakeholder group engages with open source software and hardware, governance and recognition in different ways, while tailoring communication, functionalities, and value propositions to their specific contexts is essential. For industry and open source players and developer communities (primary stakeholders), this may mean access to a credible, transparent, and merit-based recognition framework that validates their contributions at a European level, while for policy makers (primary stakeholders) and funding bodies/investors (secondary stakeholders) is more related to evidence-based insights to inform digital sovereignty strategies, public procurement of open source solutions and broader technology governance. On the other hand, general public (secondary stakeholders) benefit from enhanced awareness of open source values, features, increased digital literacy and greater participation in the open source ecosystem.

Aligning OS Awards.eu's Key Exploitable Results (KERs) with these goals ensures greater adoption of open-source principles within Europe, while strengthening collaboration between communities and institutions and maximising the project's impact on the sustainable development of an open, innovative and sovereign European digital landscape.

KER N°	Name	Description	Stakeholders
1	European Open Source Academy and Awards Framework	The governance model, and operational framework underpinning both the European Open Source Academy and the European Open Source Awards. The Academy provides a formal, European-level vehicle for recognising, educating, and connecting open source talent and communities, while the Awards serve as the flagship mechanism for celebrating excellence and merit in open source contribution across Europe. Together, they constitute a replicable and sustainable institutional framework that can endure beyond the project's lifetime	Policymakers Industry Players Open Source Professionals
2	Strategy for OS Skills Development	A strategic roadmap that outlines how open-source competencies can be systematically nurtured across different profiles, from students and developers to public sector professionals and industry practitioners. The strategy provides recommendations for embedding open source skills into formal and informal education, as well as education experiences, namely through masterclasses and webinars.	Open Source Professionals
3	Thought-Leadership Outputs and Tools	Reports, white papers, policy briefs, visualisation tools and analytical outputs produced by the project that position the European Open Source Academy and the Awards as authoritative voices in the open source space. The Visualisation Tool (to be launched but already in early development stages) offers a data-driven lens on the open source ecosystem in Europe.	Policymakers Industry Players Investors and Funding Bodies

Table 1 Overview of OSAwards.eu KERs and stakeholders

Having in mind these KERs and the stakeholder groups, this report provides an overview of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities performed by OSAwards.eu, detailed in the following chapters.

2 Communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement plan and interim report

2.1 Brand identities

The European Open Source Academy (EOSA) and OS Awards.EU each have distinct brand identities, designed for clarity, adaptability, and strong visual presence across digital and print platforms. The EOSA logo, with its blue gradient, represents professionalism, trust, and the journey from knowledge to expertise, aligning with its role in education and skills development. In contrast, the OS Awards logo, featuring dark grey and gold tones, conveys prestige and celebration, reinforcing its function as a high-profile recognition platform for open source contributions. Both logos are optimised for various formats and backgrounds, ensuring readability and consistency. Detailed brand guidelines, including colour palettes and usage rules, are provided in Appendix III.

Figure 1 Logos of EOSA & the Awards

2.2 Channels Overview

2.2.1 Website

The OS Awards.eu project disseminates its updates primarily through the EOSA website, which serves as its main digital communication channel, complemented by a dedicated website for the annual European Open Source Awards ceremony, as outlined in D7.1. Figure 2 illustrates the status of website development, which has reached Release 2.0. This phase was initiated with the launch of new sections, followed by the progressive development of additional ones over subsequent months. At the time of writing, several sections have been completed, while others remain under development.

Figure 2 Timeline of the Website Releases 2025-2027

Release 2.0

This release represents a significant improvement, providing the community with a more comprehensive overview of the project’s activities and highlighting initiatives relevant to different stakeholder groups. The sections below detail the work carried out in recent months. It is important to note that these releases, as well as the ongoing developments, reflect feedback collected throughout the reporting period, with the aim of better addressing the needs of the EOSA community.

As the EuropeanOS Awards project reaches its mid-point, greater prominence is being given to its key results, particularly on the [homepage](#). A redesigned version of the homepage, already approved, is currently under development and is expected to go live in May. In this updated version, core components of the project (namely the Awards Ceremony, policy activities, and skills and training) are more prominently featured, with direct access provided through both the main navigation menu and the hero section. Meanwhile, news and events are repositioned further down the page to support a clearer and more structured user experience.

Figure 3 Visual Mock-up approved for the new EOSA homepage

As an academy by nature, EOSA is supported by an Academy Board that shapes its activities and serves as a group of European ambassadors, promoting excellence across key areas of open source. To reflect this structure, a dedicated **Academy section**¹ has been created under the “About Us” area of the website. This section presents the Academy members, organised according to their domains

¹ <https://europeanopensource.academy/about/academy-members>

of expertise: Advocacy and Awareness, Business and Impact, and Skills and Education, alongside a dedicated subsection for the Academy Presidium members. Each member is featured on an individual page, providing an overview of their profile and experience within the open-source ecosystem.

Figure 4 Academy members section (left) & dedicated page for an Academy Member (right)

An academy can only fulfil its purpose through the strength and engagement of its members. Following the establishment of EOSA’s founding pillars, and while progressing towards its full formal recognition as an institution beyond the project, it is essential to attract new partners in order to foster community growth and strengthen its relevance within the European and global landscape. To support this objective, a dedicated **“Partnership” section** has been created in April 2026 (to be made available in the website by in May 2026), outlining the different partnership models available for supporting the Academy. This section provides a clear description of each model, along with the associated benefits for prospective partners, thereby facilitating engagement and long-term collaboration with the EOSA initiative.

To highlight the growing interest in both the project and the European Open Source Awards, a dedicated **“Press and Media” section** has been introduced, with direct access from the main menu of the EOSA website. This section is structured into two main pages:

- **Press Releases²**: with all press releases issued during the project timeframe, as well as information indicating that media and press representatives are welcome to contact the EOSA communications team for further details on EOSA activities. (see Figure 5 on the left).
- **Academy in the Press³**: provides an overview of how the community perceives EOSA. This section highlights external mentions and references, demonstrating the appreciation of the open-source community for the work carried out by the project. It also serves as evidence of

² <https://europeanopensource.academy/press-releases>

³ <https://europeanopensource.academy/press-media/academy-in-the-press>

the relevance and impact of EOSA within the broader open-source ecosystem (see Figure 5 on the right).

Figure 5 Press Releases section (left) and Academy in the press (right) website sections

EOSA aims to play an active role in European policymaking by contributing to digital sovereignty through the development of policy recommendations, training materials and policy-oriented workshops that support the advancement of open-source-centric digital policies. Given the importance of this work, a dedicated **Policy section**⁴ has been introduced, accessible directly from the main menu. This section provides users with easy access to all EOSA materials and activities relevant to EU policy development. At present, it includes an initial policy brief, as well as news articles produced by EOSA on related topics.

⁴ [Open Source in European Policy | European Open Source Academy](#)

Figure 6 EOSA Policy section

Skills and training are a fundamental component of EOSA, as they ensure that individuals and organizations can effectively participate in, contribute to, and benefit from open-source ecosystems. Open source is not solely about access to code; it also requires a strong foundation in technical, collaborative, and problem-solving skills. Through the provision of structured training, the Academy helps bridge skills gaps across regions, promotes digital inclusion, and empowers developers, researchers, and businesses to innovate more effectively. Ultimately, strengthening skills across the ecosystem contributes to a more resilient, competitive, and collaborative European digital landscape. In this context, a dedicated **“Skills and Training” section** has been launched within EOSA, comprising multiple elements that are being progressively released, refined, and enriched throughout the project lifecycle.

To begin with, one of the most anticipated features of the website is the **Data Visualisation Tool**. At the time of writing, some predefined dashboard are accessible via a sub-section under the “Skills and resources” area of the EOSA website. The Data Visualisation Tool is a digital platform intended to be used to map and analyse Europe’s presence in the global open-source ecosystem, transforming complex datasets into accessible and meaningful visual insights. At present, the EOSA website includes an intro [overview page](#)⁵, accompanied by a call to action encouraging visitors to subscribe to the newsletter in order to receive updates on future releases. This introductory page is complemented by a [blogpost](#)⁶, authored by EOSA contributors, which provides an example of the type of insights and analysis that could be done through the Data Visualisation Tool.

⁵ <https://europeanopensource.academy/open-source-data-visualisation-tool>

⁶ <https://europeanopensource.academy/open-source-data-visualisation-tool-europes-digital-future-demands-investment-not-austerity-and>

The blog post presents a preliminary set of insights into Europe’s role and relevance within the global open-source landscape. The page currently features visually engaging graphics, enabling users to apply filters and explore the data dynamically in the dashboard available for each graphic. These interactive graphs are already accessible via links included in the blog post for users who wish to test them; however, the full Data Visualisation Tool is not accessible directly from this page at this stage, as is still under development. The final version of the tool is being developed by EOSA and it is expected to be fully implemented in October 2026.

Figure 7 Data Visualisation Tool “homepage” (left), Blogspot (center) and Interactive graphic (right)

In addition to raising awareness of European open-source insights, EOSA aims to establish a training academy dedicated to strengthening open-source skills across Europe. This academy will comprise EOSA-developed training activities, including masterclasses, as well as an online catalogue of third-party training resources. Together, these components will provide a unified digital space where users can easily access relevant open-source learning materials and support awareness-raising efforts. EOSA Masterclasses, ranging from 20 minutes to one hour in length, are available on the EOSA YouTube channel and are also accessible through the EOSA website, under the recently launched “Skills and Training” section.

The online catalogue of external training materials is currently under development; the corresponding website section is already in place and is being progressively populated with a curated list of identified resources, with further additions planned for the coming months. The catalogue is organised across several dimensions to facilitate user navigation and resource discovery:

- **Thematic areas:** include Open Source Hardware, Cloud and DevOps, Governance and Public Administration, Management, Business Models, Licences and Legal Matters, Data, Multi-topic Open Source content, Infrastructure, Education Tools, Cybersecurity, IoT, Artificial Intelligence, Edge Computing, and other related domains;
- **Type:** courses, training materials, guides, blog posts, videos, webinars, forums, textbooks, case studies, podcasts, and other formats;
- **Costs:** free or paid;
- **Source:** EOSA-produced or external.

Web	Name	Description of the institution	Thematic Axes	Resource Type	link to resource
https://ocwcommons.org/	Commons Open Education Resources	Open Educational Resources (OER) offer opportunities for systemic change in teaching and learning content through engaging educators in new participatory processes and effective technologies for engaging with learning. Explore, create, and collaborate with educators around the world to improve curriculum.	Multiple topics related to open source	Courses Textbooks Labs Case study	https://ocwcommons.org/search?base=ocw:homepage&f_ssort=ocw:open-source&f_subject=At:subject%3A%2Fopen-source
https://www.oshwa.org/	Open Source Hardware Association	The OSHWA aim to foster technological knowledge and encourage research that is accessible, collaborative and respects user freedom. OSHWA is hosting a number of strategy and visioning sessions to collect community responses from open hardware health device creators and medical stakeholders.	General information about open source hardware and its socially beneficial uses.	Open Source Hardware Certification Conferences and events Education Best Practices for Open Source Hardware Guidelines and videos Journal Articles Dissertation Fellowships	https://oshwa.org/resources/ https://oshwa.org/programs/
https://www.classcentral.com/	Class Central	Class Central is a listing of online courses. We aggregate courses from many providers to make it easy to find the best courses on almost any subject, wherever they exist. Whatever you are interested in learning, it is more than likely that our catalog includes a course that will meet your needs.	Multiple topics related to open source	Courses	https://www.classcentral.com/institute/some-open-source
https://www.eclipse.org/	The Eclipse Foundation	The Eclipse Foundation provides our global community of individuals and organisations with a mature, scalable, and business-friendly environment for open source software collaboration and innovation. We have a proven track record of enabling community-led and industry-ready open	Developer Tools & IDEs Cloud Native Edge & IoT Automotive & Mobility	Forums Blogs and videos News Guidelines Success Stories Industry Expert Testimonials	https://www.eclipse.org/org/value https://newsroom.eclipse.org/ https://www.eclipse.org/forum/ https://www.eclipse.org/blogs-an-videos/

Figure 8 List of Preliminary Materials identified to be made available in the online catalogue

As mentioned, updates implemented within EOSA have also been accompanied by enhancements to the **European Open Source Awards online presence**. Compared to the 2025 edition, which consisted of a single page providing general information about the ceremony, the 2026 edition has been upgraded into a fully-fledged website⁷. This expanded platform includes detailed information on the 2025 awardees, the nomination process, a comprehensive agenda featuring high-level speakers, and the announcement of the 2026 awardees (presented live during the 2026 ceremony), as well as venue details and other relevant information.

Figure 9 Snapshot of European OS Awards website in 2026

⁷ <https://awards.europeanopensource.academy/>

For both the Academy website and the Awards mini-site, we have opted to use open source tools such as Matomo in order to track the visitors retention and growth over the months. With the deployment of new website sections and the growth of the Academy, the visitor growth over the period of M5 until M18 has marked a growth of 869.06%, indicating a consistent growth over the course of the project. The largest jump occurred between M10 and M11, with an 81.53% increase due to announcement of 3rd webinar, EOSA Magazine call for submissions, and the beginning of the call for nominations for the 2nd Annual European Open Source Awards. The number of visitors peaked naturally with the delivery of the Awards Ceremony when we recorded 4030 site visits. Given the option to opt out of the cookie tracking policies, these numbers only reflect those who have accepted the websites' cookie policies, which in the case of this project is averaging on 21% acceptance rate.

Future Releases

As indicated in Figure 2, two additional releases are planned for the following year. The first is scheduled for October 2026 and will focus on the full launch of the Data Visualisation Tool, alongside the introduction of additional website sections. A second and final release is foreseen approximately one year later after the submission of this report and will consolidate all project outcomes, including the third edition of the European Open-Source Awards in 2027. This final release will also consider the formal establishment of EOSA as an institution, enabling it to welcome new members and further support the European Union in shaping its digital sovereignty

Social Media and Content Repositories

In the initial phase of the project (M1-M18), OS Awards.EU has established itself as a trusted voice regarding the latest opportunities, open source achievements and individuals spearheading the advancements of open source in Europe. In order to engage a diverse range of stakeholders, from developers, businesses, and researcher institutions, OS Awards.EU devised and implemented a multi-faceted strategy orchestrating information, communication, and marketing activities.

Social Media channels have proven to be the main device of keeping attention and fostering conversation amongst the projects' audience. Since the start of the project's operational work, OS Awards.EU has actively built an online presence through social media platforms: **LinkedIn, Mastodon, Bluesky, YouTube, and Zenodo**. Through frequent posts, diverse formats of engagement such as articles, videos, masterclasses and carousels, the OS Awards.EU project strives to raise the Academy's profile and visibility, credibility and to increase the awareness and prestigiousness of the European Open Source Awards.

As of M18, OS Awards.EU has over **3,762 followers** on social media (in comparison to 1,160 followers in M05, representing a growth of +220%). Given the expansion of the Academy membership, and with two very visible editions of the European Open Source Awards, the project has successfully established itself as a platform for the open source community, and can be confirmed by the consistently raising number of followers, and number of interactions collected by the in-built analytics tools.

For 2026-2027, OSAwards.EU will continue to implement its communications activities by utilising the social media tools and sharing compelling and up-to-date content for its stakeholders. With particular interest to our stakeholders, OSAwards.EU will showcase **Academy-driven opinion pieces**, various editions of **community-led European Open Source Magazine**, delivery of the latest **masterclasses**, and **participation at internal and external events**, and thereby amplifying its efforts and guarantee the establishment of a consolidated and engaged online community.

Moreover, an engaged community are future potential attendees and nominees of the European Open Source Awards, thus ensuring credibility and garnering interests around EOSA and its Awards. In addition, the OSAwards.EU project will complement its work with frequent topic research to continuously be aware of the needs and interests of the target audience and measure its efforts success in relation to KPIs.

2.2.1.1 LinkedIn

Considering the primary audience of OSAwards.EU includes the professional network of open source contributors, LinkedIn represents the essential platform that allows users to connect around shared interests and highlight opportunities for the open source community. In the case of OSAwards.EU⁸, we utilise LinkedIn as a platform to spread awareness about Academy, latest opportunities and engaging call to actions regarding nomination processes, Magazine submissions and other, to a vast audience. By publishing timely and diverse content on LinkedIn, OSAwards.EU has established active online community of open source experts and non-expert and addresses the need for quality content on European based solutions and initiatives.

Figure 10 EOSA LinkedIn Snapshot

2.2.1.2 Mastodon

Mastodon operates based on open source decentralised, federated servers, with each server garnering in particular the attention and engagement of specific interest groups. OSAwards.EU is

⁸ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eosacademy1>

represented on this platform via its channel⁹, with a unique opportunity to creating tailor made content for the open source community, such as developers, open source initiatives, and businesses. Albeit a smaller number of users, Mastodon is particularly used by specialised relevant audiences, presenting a way for meaningful engagement through concise short messages, and establishment of the EOSA as a recognisable institution amongst its peers.

Figure 11 EOSA Mastodon snapshot

2.2.1.3 Bluesky

In order to promulgate the use of alternative, specialised platforms with a consideration of transparency and data regulation, OS Awards.EU opted for the use of Bluesky¹⁰ over X, moving all our short-format posts and closing the previously established account. The decision was made given the deterioration of X’s regulation and the increasing use of Bluesky, with its open communication protocols. In a similar format to X’s micro-blogging, Bluesky allows to share concise messages and reach out to interest specific audiences. The platform is used for concise and immediate updates, a feature especially useful live event updates, which was utilised during the 2nd Annual European Open Source Awards.

Figure 12 EOSA Bluesky snapshot

⁹ <https://fosstodon.org/@europeanOSAcademy>

¹⁰ <https://bsky.app/profile/eosa.bsky.social>

2.2.1.4 YouTube

Through the initial phase of the project, a range of video content has proven to be essential in the effective communication about the scope and impact of open source in Europe, and to reflect the impressions of the open source community. In its YouTube channel¹¹, the project has established a curated list of masterclasses, webinars, reflections from third party events like UN Open Source Week, or FOSDEM, and it’s the main repository of short-form videos. We have also began using PeerTube with the latest webinar delivered in M18, in order to support and raise awareness about the decentralised, community-drive platforms.

Figure 13 EOSA YouTube snapshot

2.2.1.5 Zenodo

As detailed in D7.1, ZENODO is the online open repository where the public deliverables and other research outputs will be made available. The ZENODO community of European Open Source Awards was created¹² and materials will be added in the following days after the submission of this deliverable D7.2

Figure 14 Landing page of OS Awards.EU ZENODO Community

¹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/@EuropeanOpenSourceAcademy>.

¹² <https://zenodo.org/communities/osawards/>

2.2.2 OS Awards.EU-Driven Events

Building visibility and rapport with different EOSA audiences remains a central priority, with a series of targeted events being organised and well attended and followed, throughout the project in line with clear objectives, defined stakeholder audiences and expected output.

Academy events continue to play a key role in fostering collaboration and engagement within the European Open Source ecosystem, namely the OS Academy Masterclass series¹³.

Figure 15 Example of a presentation image of a EOSA Masterclass

This series is now well underway: the first edition has been successfully produced and released, the 7 episodes are openly accessible in a dedicated playlist¹⁴ on the YouTube Channel of the project and already more than 620 views have been attracted. The preparations for the second – and following - editions are currently in progress.

This mixed palette of events provides a concrete platform for EOSA members to showcase expertise in key aspects of Open Source Software and Hardware, helping the broader ecosystem develop awareness and understanding of excellence in those fields. The Academy also promotes recognition and advocacy for Open Source Software and Hardware excellence, highlighting outstanding contributions through nominations and public events, encouraging further involvement in the OS movement.

Date	Proposed Topics/Focus	Target Audience & Number of registrations/views	
15 Jan 2025 (Delivered)	Webinar: Open Source for Responsible & Trustworthy AI: "decoding" the potential of European Open Source Community ¹⁵	Academics, Industry Leaders, Developers, Innovators, Policymakers	70 registrants

¹³ https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL5wPUz5V53R_N3upOy_eRJdAakVD3rMvA

¹⁴ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6Gt_VwvS9yw&list=PL5wPUz5V53R_N3upOy_eRJdAakVD3rMvA

¹⁵ <https://europeanopensource.academy/events/open-source-responsible-and-trustworthy-ai-decoding-potential-european-open-source-community>

Date	Proposed Topics/Focus	Target Audience & Number of registrations/views	
3 June 2025 (Delivered)	Webinar: Open Source for Cybersecurity : Securing and Maintaining Europe's Open Source Dependencies ¹⁶	Developers, Policymakers, Industry Stakeholders	90 registrants
29 Sept 2025 (Delivered)	Webinar: Open source contributions to standardisation: opportunities ahead ¹⁷	Innovators, Developers Academics	122 registrants
Jan-Feb 2026	EOS Academy Masterclass: Building, Sustaining, and Securing Source Impact with Amandine Le Pape Security From grassroots origins to powering government-level infrastructures, this masterclass shows how to take an open protocol to the mainstream.	Industry Stakeholders, Policymakers, Developers	+620 total views
8 Apr 2026 (Delivered)	Webinar: Breaking Cloud Lock-in: The Role of Open Source and Standards in Creating a Competitive Cloud Market ¹⁸	Community Managers, Developers, Academics, Industry Stakeholders	78 registrants
June 2026 (expected)	Webinar: The Future of Open Hardware Exploring the potential for open hardware to revolutionise industries like manufacturing and electronics.	Engineers, Hardware Developers	
June-July 2026 (expected)	E OS Academy Masterclass: The importance of community in building and sustaining open source with Lydia Pintscher	Academics, Developers, Innovators	
Q3 2026	Webinar: Open Source in Industry Content of this webinar are still to be confirmed.	Policymakers, Industry Stakeholders, Developers	
Q1 2027	Workshop: OS Academy Masterclass: Teaching Open Source and Open Hardware Skills with David Cuartielles For educators and open hardware tinkerers, this masterclass explores how to design hands-on learning experiences that demystify electronics and coding.	Policymakers, Public Sector Leaders, Academics, Hardware Developers	

Table 2 Overview of EOSA events organised and planned ones

The preliminary plan for future events may be subject to changes pending validation by the academy members.

2.2.3 Events – Third-Party

The project garnered visibility by active participation of OS Awards.EU partners and EOSA Academy Members in relevant third-party events (both on-site and virtual including podcasts) as speakers,

¹⁶ <https://europeanopensource.academy/events/open-source-cybersecurity-securing-and-maintaining-europes-open-source-dependencies>

¹⁷ <https://europeanopensource.academy/events/open-source-contributions-standardisation-opportunities-ahead>

¹⁸ <https://europeanopensource.academy/events/breaking-cloud-lock-role-open-source-and-standards-creating-competitive-cloud-market>

panel participants, workshops facilitators, or posters presenters. Attendance at events has a strategic value for the project including:

- The promotion of OS Awards.EU work to different target stakeholders and establishing ourselves as a trusted voice in the open source community;
- Collection of new contacts for database enrichment and collaboration opportunities;
- Engage directly to new potential open source audiences;
- Develop synergies with different organisations and initiatives, for potential collaboration;
- Dissemination of EOSA project findings and engagement with the open source community;
- Increasing the visibility of open source through business, advocacy, and education fields.

An Event Tracker allows members and consortium members to log their attendance at industry events, amplifying EOSA's visibility and ensuring key messages reach broader audiences. This tool also supports content creation for media office outreach and social media campaigns, strengthening advocacy efforts. The OS Awards.EU partners and EOSA members aim to promote the project or Open Source in general at some events, as listed in the table below. Additional events for the upcoming year can also be found. Since the beginning of the project, **19 third-party events** have had project or Academy Member promotion or project visibility. Below we indicate the most relevant events that occurred between M10 and M18.

N	Event	Date/s	Location	OS Awards.EU/EOSA Representative & Form of Visibility
1	The Matrix Conference	15-18 Oct 2025	Strasbourg, France	Amandine Le Pape (EOSA) – Co-hosts
2	Decidim Fest	4-5 Nov 2025	Barcelona, Spain	Amandine Le Pape (EOSA) - Participant
3	Gaia-X Summit	20-21 Nov 2025	Porto, Portugal	Francisca Rubio, GAIA-X Spain General Manager, presented OS Awards on behalf of Tecnalia (Tecnalia, OS Awards.eu) - Presentation
4	Open Source Experience	10-11 Dec 2025	Paris, France	Amandine Le Pape (EOSA) - Participant
5	EU Open Source Policy Summit	30 Jan 2026	Brussels, Belgium	Daniel Stenberg (EOSA) – Panellist
6	FOSDEM'26	31 Jan 2026	Brussels, Belgium	Nick Gates (OFE, OS Awards.eu) – Workshop presenter
7	NDC Security	4-5 Mar 2026	Oslo, Norway	Daneil Stenberg (EOSA) – Workshop presenter
8	MWC Conference	4-5 Mar 2026	Barcelona, Spain	Maritza Luis Perez (BSC, OS Awards.eu) – Exhibition presenter
9	FOSS Backstage	16-17 Mar 2026	Berlin, Germany	Nick Gates (OFE, OS Awards.eu) – Panelist

Table 3 EOSA presence at third-party events

2.2.4 Email outreach, newsletters and the EOSA Magazine

The initial communication plan entailed the publication of a newsletter every three months, with the content shaped around important EOSA developments featuring news, events, and articles published on the EOSA website. However, given the revision of the Grant Agreement on 20 November 2025 the priority has been given to other communication activities, such as the production of bi-annual European Open Source Magazine, and to one to one email outreach to the events' and EOSAwards participants' database.

The first issue of the European Open Source Magazine¹⁹ has received contributions from 32 individuals representing developers, business leads, policy makers and Academy members, writing about the most timely topics concerning the open source community. Around 80 physical copies have been disseminated during the 2nd Annual European Open Source Awards. The call for the contributions to the second issue has opened on 1st of April and will remain open until 15th of May.

Nevertheless, the ability to subscribe to the newsletter still remained and those acquired contacts have been contacted through emails about the aforementioned EOSA activities. The collection of these contacts complies with the GDPR and the EOSA Privacy Policy.

Figure 16 Cover of 1st EOSA Magazine

2.2.5 Press and Media

During this second reporting period, press and media visibility has reached a noticeably more mature level of engagement. Communication efforts have been structured around targeted briefings and meetings, serving a dual purpose: internally, they have helped coordinate actions and align the global message across consortium partners and Academy members; externally, they have

¹⁹ <https://europeanopensource.academy/eosa-magazine/issue-1>

supported outreach to journalists and press contacts, ensuring a coherent and unified communication front.

OS Awards Event campaign

Campaign activity, coverage secured, and audiences reached: In connection with the OS Awards ceremony held in Brussels in January 2026, two press releases (PR1²⁰ & PR2²¹, available in the PR section of EOSA website²²) were prepared and strategically disseminated to a broad network of media and press contacts. Trust-IT Services, the consortium's Communication and Dissemination partner, leveraged its established media relationships and sectoral expertise to secure coverage across both specialised and general-interest outlets. Consortium partners were equally engaged in this effort, receiving guidance and support to actively contribute to the dissemination of results and key achievements. The resulting media campaign produced substantial visibility within the open-source and more general ecosystem.

Figure 17 Snapshot of a PR focused on European OS Awards 2026

The Open Source Awards 2026 campaign specifically generated coverage across a range of sectors, with a strong concentration in open source, developer, and specialist technology media. Key placements appeared in platforms such as Linuxiac, It's FOSS, OSTechNix and Nextcloud, reflecting deep engagement within the core open source. The pie chart below depicts the distribution of articles produced, categorised by media sector, while the other graphic on the right illustrates the distribution of articles categorised by media type.

²⁰ <https://europeanopensource.academy/news/new-awards-honour-quiet-builders-europes-digital-world>

²¹ <https://europeanopensource.academy/news/brussels-stages-nobel-prize-open-source-europe-honours-digital-pioneers>

²² <https://europeanopensource.academy/press-releases>

Most of the coverage appeared in specialist and community-led media, including open source platforms, developer-focused publications, and institutional channels. This reflects the nature of the story, where credibility and relevance are strongest within expert communities. Overall, it should also be noted that the coverage reported reflect results generated directly through formal media outreach and dissemination activities, plus additional visibility has been achieved through project and partner channels.

A selection of media coverage is illustrated in the figure below, accompanied by the corresponding monthly visit metrics for each outlet. **A comprehensive list of 32 media coverage articles is provided** in Appendix II. It should be noted that press and media engagement is an ongoing process; therefore, additional articles may have been published after the drafting of this document.

Title	URL	Media Type	Country	Sector	Monthly Visits
1 Next Cloud	https://nextcloud.com/blog/nextcloud-os-and-founder-frank-karlitschek-wins-european-open-source-award-for-business-impact/	Corporate Blog	Germany	Open Source	1,632,000
2 ITS Foss	https://itsfoss.com/news/greg-knoah-hartman-european-open-source-award/	Industry Media	Global (India)	Open Source	964,606
3 Télécom Paris	https://www.telecom-paris.fr/european-open-source-award-software-heritage	Industry Media	France	Open Source	459,956
4 Linuxiac (Awards article)	https://linuxiac.com/european-open-source-awards-2026-honor-greg-knoah-hartman	Trade Media	Global (US)	Linux	226,878
5 Science Business	https://sciencebusiness.net/news/recognition-open-source-trailblazers	Trade Media	Belgium	EU Science News	126,329
6 OSTechNix	https://ostechnix.com/greg-knoah-hartman-open-source-award-2026/	Trade Media	Global (India)	Open Source	114,178
7 Gardiner Bryant	https://gardinerbryant.com/interview-with-european-open-source-award-winners-greg-kh-jenny-motley-and-frank-karlitschek/	Independent	UK	Technology	81,734
8 Tecnalia	https://www.tecnalia.com/en/news/tecnalia-reinforces-its-commitment-to-open-source	Trade Media	Spain	Applied Research	42,790
9 OSS Directory	https://www.ossdirectory.com/en/topnews/details/verisfun-g-der-european-open-source-awards-2026	Aggregator	Germany	Open Source	5,314
10 NGI Commons	https://commons.ngi.eu/event/european-open-source-awards-2026/	Blog	EU (Netherlands)	Digital Innovation	500

Figure 19 List of media coverage with monthly visit metrics

Last week, Frank Karlistschek, CEO and founder of Nextcloud, received the Special Recognition for Contributions to Business & Impact Award at the European Open Source Awards (EOSA) 2026.

And while his name was called on stage, Frank wanted to highlight that this accomplishment is shared with the entire Nextcloud community, without whom it wouldn't have been possible.

From contributors and translators to testers, partners, and users advocating for digital sovereignty every day: this award reflects a collective effort to prove that open source is impactful, competitive, and ready for Europe's digital future.

Figure 20 Example of article (part1)

SCIENCE|BUSINESS
Bringing together industry, research and policy

News ▾ Funding News ▾ Reports ▾ Events ▾ The Network ▾ Communications Services ▾ About Us ▾

Recognition for open source trailblazers

Supported by European Open Source Academy | More news about European Open Source Academy

12 Feb 2026 | News

At the second annual European Open Source Awards, Greg Kroah-Hartman received the main prize in recognition of his "outstanding impact" in open source software development, technical leadership and sustained excellence over several decades.

Greg Kroah-Hartman receiving the award for outstanding impact in open source software development
Photo Credits: Trust-IT

"I feel very privileged and honoured that my peers have recognised the work I have done for so long," Greg Kroah-Hartman, a fellow of the Linux Foundation, told the awards ceremony at the historic Bibliothèque Solvay in Brussels on 29th January. "But it is not just me, there are tens of thousands of developers doing this work," he added, emphasising long-lasting solutions as a core strength of the open source community. "Writing code once is really easy, making it work for 25 years is a totally different kind of engineering. The open source community is really good at that. It is like maintaining a bridge for 100 years."

Hosted by the European Open Source Academy and supported by the EU-funded project OS Awards EU, the ceremony recognised the human stories behind Europe's digital infrastructure - much of which is based on open source technology - including developers and community leaders whose work sustains everything from cloud computing and AI to healthcare, energy systems, and public services.

Digital engineering requires a steady flow of talent, Kroah-Hartman noted. The next generation has always been important for the Linux kernel developer, who has worked with universities since starting out in the 1990s. "I want students to get involved and always tell them the best way to get a job is to start a project while studying," he said. "It gives them something to show later

Linux's Second-in-Command Greg Kroah-Hartman Bestowed With The European Open Source Award

Linux kernel maintainer honored at Brussels ceremony for decades of critical infrastructure work.

Sourav Rudra
02 Feb 2026 · 2 min read · 0 comments

We already know that open source maintainers aren't as valued as they should be, and working endlessly without a goal in mind or some appropriate compensation just ends up breaking them.

The European Open Source Academy (EOSA) recognizes open source leaders through its annual awards. *The Prize for Excellence in Open Source Software* goes to people who've made outstanding contributions.

Daniel Stenberg, the president of the academy and also creator of curl, has announced that Greg Kroah-Hartman is among the awardees for this year.

In addition to Kroah-Hartman, the following individuals were honoured for their remarkable contributions to the open source community:

- **Advocacy and Awareness category:** Jenny Molloy, senior research associate, Shuttleworth Research Fellow, University of Cambridge, GOSH - for ensuring open source is included in the policymaking agenda, and raising awareness of open source technologies.
- **Business and Impact category:** Frank Karlistschek, CEO and founder of Nextcloud - for paving the way for open source innovation, commercialisation and impact, showcasing that open source is a key component of European digital competitiveness.
- **Community Impact category:** Roberto Di Cosmo and Stefano Zacchiroli, founders of Software Heritage - for positive impact on the open source ecosystem and advancing the interests of open source collaboration and innovation
- **Skills and Education category:** Matthew Venn, founder of Tiny Tapeout - for pioneering educational projects and initiatives advancing open source skills, education, knowledge.

Helping Europe pursue digital sovereignty

The European Open Source Awards formed as a key part of the EU Open Source Week, a week-long series of events bringing together a range of stakeholders to recognise outstanding contributions to open source software, hardware and open technologies. Such initiatives highlight open source as an increasingly hot topic, which in recent years has gained more awareness beyond the digital community.

Policymakers are starting to take note, with the European Commission, among others, advocating the use of open source software to foster innovation, security, and digital sovereignty. The European Open Source Awards, which were attended by Thibaut Kleiner, director for future networks in DG Connect and other representatives of the European Commission, Member State Permanent Representatives and MEPs, help to forge political relations and raise awareness in broader terms.

"The examples we honour tonight add credibility when we are approached by European lawmakers. Digital sovereignty would simply not be possible without open source software," noted Amandine Le Page, head of section at the Open Source Academy. "Without transparency, there is no trust and no control. You want control over where to host your software and the ability to switch vendor or take your data and move it somewhere else."

Building longevity and sustainability

Transparency and holistic, long-term thinking also resonate with Roberto Di Cosmo and Stefano Zacchiroli. The founders of Software Heritage, which shared the Community Impact prize, are celebrating 10 years of collecting and preserving software in source code form. "Sustainability is a common challenge for all open source initiatives. We need to lay the ground to make sure that the archive is there, not just 10 years from now, but 100-200 years from now," said Zacchiroli.

As a UNESCO partnered project, Software Heritage underlines open source as a discipline with wide-branching relevance and defies the notion of data as easily replaced or replicated. Standing next to the Bibliothèque Solvay's ceiling-high shelves of timeworn paper, Zacchiroli stressed digital code's role to society: "It is really important to have a trace of what is built. If you lose an essential piece of source code, which makes critical society infrastructure work, that is a disaster."

By celebrating the innovators behind open source technology, the European Open Source Awards aim to highlight what open source is, what it is capable of and why it is important. Over the next 12 months, the Open Source Academy will continue to persuade decision-makers across the continent to recognise the importance of open source, support the people creating these technologies, and invest in sustaining and securing them.

Figure 21 Example of article (part2)

Website - Academy on the press section

A dedicated section “Academy in the press²³” has been set up on the website to showcase press clippings related to the media presence of both the event and the Academy. This section also serves as a platform through which visitors may directly contact the press office, as well as submit enquiries and press releases.

Figure 22 "Academy in Press" section on EOSA website

2.3 Campaigns

The C&D campaigns for the **OS Awards.eu rests upon four core campaigns**, with significant success established in raising awareness and securing engagement with the European OS Academy and the Awards. Since M18, the project has also introduced additional three sub-campaigns that include:

- Nominations to the European Open Source Awards;
- The call for contributions to the European Open Source Magazine;
- Partnership Acquisition, with initial data to come in during the next months.

Some of the key performance indicators tracked here will be the outreach efforts to unique organisations, number of disseminated copies and views of partnership brochures, Magazines and nomination info packs. Additionally, WP7 team is also monitoring how the submission numbers for the Magazine and for the Awards Ceremony nominations have increased in comparison to last year’s edition. On a monthly basis, the project monitors various key performance indicators, such as website views, social media followers, and webinar attendees. In the table below, it is indicated some of the Key Performance Indicators over the course of project start to M05. The tables do not include all KPIs currently monitored by the EOSA team.

²³ <https://europeanopensource.academy/press-media/academy-in-the-press>

2.3.1 Campaign 1: Branding and Awareness & Recurring Activities

While the branding identity of the Academy and the Awards Ceremony are now distinguishable and recognisable, there are several activities that are still ongoing to ensure the continuation and visibility of visual identity. Through a series of videos, weekly social media posts, community members garnered from events and post engagement, Campaign 1 has served to establish the recognisability of the EOSA and Awards brands within the EU and global OS ecosystem and across all target groups. Additional monitoring also involves website visitors and publication views.

Indicators	Target	Frequency	Status	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10
Social Media Posts	4	Weekly	On-track	20	16	42	27	18
Community Members	1,000	By end	Ongoing	300	312	312	312	434
Website Visitors	15,000		Needs att'n	408	488	507	867	823
Indicators	Target	Frequency	Status	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15
Social Media Posts	4	Weekly	On-track	42	30	30	15	81
Community Members	1,000	By end	Ongoing	434	500	500	650	650
Website Visitors	15,000		Needs att'n	884	823	1494	1844	2220
Indicators	Target	Frequency	Status	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20
Social Media Posts	4	Weekly	On-track	42	39	51	TBD	TBD
Community Members	1,000	By end	Ongoing	650	650	650	TBD	TBD
Website Visitors	15,000		Needs att'n	3187	4030	4729	TBD	TBD

Table 4 Overview of Campaign 1 KIPs between M1-M20

The inaugural European Open Source Awards, as well as the nomination and delivery of the 2nd Annual European Open Source Awards have served as a significant boost to the project's visibility and as a mode establishing the project and the Academy in the open source community as an expert-led institution contributing to skills uptake and policy influence.

The culminative community has also expanded with the **delivery of additional webinars** in M8 (Open Source in Cybersecurity), M11 (Open Source and Open Standards) and M18 (Open Source and the Cloud Lock-In). Additionally, the delivery and open access of the first Masterclass series in seven-part episodes have contributed to attracting over 600 views for the entire first series. The first campaign ensures the existing community is presented with novel content, remains engaged and is frequently asked for contribution, all the while expanding and retaining new potential audience members by promoting the activities through the consortium, new knowledge partners, Magazine contributors and others.

2.3.2 Campaign 2: Academy Awareness & Promotion

The scope of this campaign encapsulates the newly formed European OS Academy and their activities, including **Academy Masterclass workshops, and thematic webinars**. While the campaign will be implemented throughout the project, it will be divided into three phases that will each aim to increase website visits, social media followers and video views:

- Phase 1 Awareness until M10;
- Phase 2 Establishment until M20, which is currently ongoing;
- Phase 3 Towards Sustainability until M30.

As part of the campaign, the following will be carried out:

- 3 masterclasses, which are pre-recorded and publicly available. First masterclass was delivered, while the second one begins production in M19;
- 4 videos: Academy presentation video, Awards & Academy members presentation video, EC on the value of open source, Resource Hub Promotional video;
- 6 webinars, with 4 webinars delivered so far;
- 3 policy & technology briefs, with 1 policy brief delivered so far in M13.

The table below reflects KPIs for the completed first phase of the second communications campaign, “Academy Phase 1 Awareness”, which lasted from M01 (Nov’24) to M10 (Aug ’25). It also includes the ongoing second phase of the second communications campaign, “Academy Phase 2 Establishment”, which will last M11 (Sep ’25) to M20 (Jun ’26).

Indicators	Target	Status	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Website Sessions Per month	200	Ongoing	111	131	200	166	155	149	339
Total Social Media Followers	200	Ongoing	1378	1512	1656	1844	1844	1973	2198
You Tube Views	150	Ongoing	222	235	263	355	378	396	462
Indicators	Target	Status	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19
Website Sessions Per month	200	Ongoing	671	350	376	967	843	490	TBD
Total Social Media Followers	200	Ongoing	2408	2475	2908	3241	3595	3764	TBD
You Tube Views	150	Ongoing	816	862	1058	1452	2072	2412	TBD

Table 5 Overview of Campaign 2 KIPs between M1-M20

A range of multimedia posts were released to increase the awareness of EOSA, their structure, and how the organisation plans to boost open source into the forefront of European technological innovation. In the second phase of the second communication campaign, this also involved producing and promoting Academy member led opinion pieces, with two published and promoted thus far. The articles led by Amandine Le Pape and Dries Buytaert include: EU's Digital Sovereignty Depends on Investment in Open Source and Talent²⁴ published also at Tech Policy Press, and When it comes to tech’s software dependency, what does ‘Buy European’ even mean?²⁵ , published at EUObserver.

After the 2nd Annual European Open Source Awards, we have produced **interviews with all the Awardees and the new Academy members**: Greg Kroah-Hartman- The Prize for Excellence in Open

²⁴ <https://europeanopensource.academy/news/eus-digital-sovereignty-depends-investment-open-source-and-talent>

²⁵ <https://europeanopensource.academy/news/when-it-comes-techs-software-dependency-what-does-buy-european-even-mean>

Source, Frank Karlitschek – Special Recognition for Business & Impact, Jenny Molloy – Special Recognition for Advocacy & Awareness, Matthew Venn – Special Recognition for Skills & Education, Stefano Zacchiroli & Roberto Di Cosmo – Special Recognition for Community Impact. These videos recapped the impressions upon receiving the recognition and serve to flag the importance of open source for Europe’s digital future. These videos will also be used as future teasers for the 3rd Awards Ceremony. **A promotional video** highlighting the events’ main outcomes was produced and has so far garnered over 160 views²⁶:

Figure 23 EOSA promotional video screenshot

During external events, such as FOSDEM’25, FOSDEM’26 and the UN Open Source Week, WP7 team has **conducted and produced 13 interviews** with key stakeholders that provided the next strategic steps, impressions about where the European open source stands. Amongst these videos, the total viewership surpassed 520 views. Based on the current KPI metrics, the project achieved the set of next targets by M20 and M30, and will continue to maintain the amount of achieved metrics.

	Campaign 2.2 Academy Phase 2 Establishment (by M20)	Campaign 2.3 Academy Phase 3 Towards Sustainability (by M30)
Website sessions per month	400	600
Total Social Media Followers	500	900
YouTube Views	350	600

Table 6 Table 7 Overview of Campaign 3 KIPs

2.3.3 Campaign 3: Flagship Event Promotion and Recruitment

This campaign is dedicated to raising awareness for the annual EU OS Awards and the new EU OS Week. The promotion of the series of EOSA ceremonies aims to engage the representatives of various entities from across the EU OS community, including foundations, industry, academia, OSPOs, policy makers, standardisation experts, and individuals. Since the event is by invitation only, the goal will not be to increase registrations but rather to build anticipation and raise the profile of the annual ceremonies establishing and positioning it as the exclusive prestigious event for the European open source community.

For the 2nd Annual European Open Source Awards, the event recording was made public and has received 182 views so far in order to reach a wider audience and garner further interest amongst

²⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FWPAj7sWe0s&t=2s>

the community for future engagement. For the 2nd European Open Source Awards, key activities delivered as a part of the campaign include:

- Delivery of promotional banners;
- An up-to-date separate mini-site for the event, accessible²⁷;
- Dedicated social media posts before, during and after the event;
- Production of videos: introductory video of the Awards and the first year of the project, post-event video highlights, video interviews with the attendees and awardees;
- Testimonial cards introducing the Master of the Ceremony, Awards Categories and others.

The table below refers to activities of 2nd Annual European Open Source Awards Ceremonies Promotion, occurring between M06 to M18.

Indicator	Target	Results	Metric
Total posts across social media	80	81	Total clicks
Website Page Views	600	967	Page views
2 nd Annual Awards Ceremony Attendees	100	149	Attendees
Post event video delivered	1	1	Video
Video Interviews Published	8	8	Videos

Table 8 Overview of Campaign 3 KIPs between M1-M18

For the establishment of a distinct sense and visual identity of European Open Source Awards, the OS Awards.EU team designed and produced a variety of promotional material, from speaker banners, roll-ups, posters, pins, and the physical OS Awards. Moreover, live updates were issued during the Inaugural Awards ceremony, ensuring the audience and those interested attending in the future are familiar with the format, award categories, and the vision behind the celebration. Several **video testimonials** from participants have been produced so far with four more planned²⁸.

Figure 24 Testimonial video screenshot

²⁷ <https://awards.europeanopensource.academy>

²⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Mj1mXm03bNw&list=PL5wPUz5V53R-15GYXWp6HUX0AAsUDJYqA>

2.3.4 Campaign 4: OS Synergies

While the previous campaigns focus on the EOSA led activities and audience retention, Campaign 4 is essential for supporting the building of synergies with established open source communities. The Academy members will be the pivotal connectors between the Awards and the EU OS landscape, since they represent a variety of backgrounds and with deep links across the entire community. In the DoA, two KPIs were laid out for synergies, 100 and 30. To reconcile this while keeping with the spirit of the KPIs, we have defined **100 total synergies** to be established, **30 of which should be high-value synergies**.

Synergies are defined in the DoA as participation to the EOSA events. This will be the minimum criteria to recognise a synergy. To be counted as a high-value synergy, the collaboration between the OS Awards.eu and/or Academy and external organisation should be conscious and ongoing. A synergy would also be referred to dedicated one-on-one meetings between the project and the external organisation, with the outcome of the meeting being the support of project's achievement of KERs. One of the avenues for facilitating synergies, and increasing visibility of relevant projects, organisations or companies working in open source, has been done through the publication of the European Open Source Academy Magazine. Given that the Magazine allows for increased visibility of contributors, but also of the EOSA project within the contributors' community, we can also **consider these to be high-value synergies**. In the first issue, eleven of external contributors have been included. In the table below, you will find the specific organisations and articles that were featured.

Organisation	Date	Contact Role	Article
Heinlein Group	January 2026	Co-CEO	Open source and the future of Europe's digital sovereignty
LINGORA	January 2026	Director of Open Source Software Assurance	Open source: the code is open, but dependence remains
Furt'her	January 2026	Board of Advisors member	Protocols: Europe's next sovereignty frontier
Eclipse Foundation	January 2026	Chief Membership Officer	Open source: the code is open, but dependence remains
Abilian	January 2026	Founder and CEO	An Architecture of Influence: The CNLL and the Industrial Maturation of France's Open Source Ecosystem
Murena	January 2026	Communication Assistant	Gaël Duval on fighting for our right to digital freedom
Mozilla Foundation	January 2026	Senior Programme Officer	The Twin Transition in open source: sustainably scaling open source projects for our climate targets
LINAGORA	January 2026	Business Development Manager	Finding each other: discovery without walled gardens
Open Science Hardware Foundation	January 2026	Board member	A decade of open science hardware: embedding openness in Europe's research ecosystem
Digital Public Goods Alliance	January 2026	Director of Policy and AI Lead	Embedding AI digital public goods into the digital sovereignty agenda
Open Logistics Foundation	January 2026	CCO	Open source and the power of diverse communities in modern logistics

Organisation	Date	Contact Role	Article	
Mozilla Collective	Data	January 2026	Senior Product Lead	Solving the AI data drought with community curated data
Martin-Luther-Universitaet Halle-Wittenberg	Halle-	January 2026	Scientific Head for open standards	Open standards for open source hardware and other high-cost-of-change domains: the missing framework

Table 9 External contributors for EOSA Magazine

The fourth campaign started its monitoring from M06, tracking the synergies established with other open source projects and initiatives in Europe. Some of the organisations we are looking to share content with and invite as contributors to OS Awards.EU project events or activities include NextCloud, the Linux Foundation, UN Open Source, Blender, Matrix.org, and many others. The following are the results of the campaign to-date. As part of the contributions made to the EOSA Magazine, we can also establish 11 additional synergies with the publication of work from lead open source contributors.

Indicators	Target	Status	M18 (Apr '26)
Total synergies established	100	Ongoing	225
- Of which, 30+ are high-value synergies	30	Ongoing	17+11 EOSA magazine synergies
Synergies webpage views by M15	150	To start	0 (website section to be launched during the next reporting period)

Table 10 Overview of Campaign 4 KIPs between M1-M18

Further information on the high-value synergies is provided below.

Organisation	Date	Contact Role	Notes
UN Open Source	25 June 2025	Open Source Coordinator	Facilitated the participation and panel contribution to the two Academy members at the UN Open Source week, held in New York City.
Radically Open Security	3 June 2025	CEO	Participated as a speaker during the 2 nd EOSA webinar.
European Cyber Security Organisation	3 June 2025	Project Officer	Participated as a speaker during the 2 nd EOSA webinar.
The Linux Foundation	3 June 2025	Senior Director	Participated as a speaker during the 2 nd EOSA webinar.
Blender	09 July 2025	CEO	One-to-one interview for a blogpost on the use of open source software in creative industries, and also Blender identified as a European success story to be promoted during the European Open Source Awards.
Unlock Open	29 September 2025	Director	Participated as a speaker during the 3 rd EOSA webinar
High Value Target	29 September 2025	CEO	Participated as the speaker during the 3 rd EOSA webinar.
FOSEM	January 2026	Event organisers	Secured speaker slots for the Academy members and two new interviews with the ecosystem representatives.
Matrix.org	February 2026	Co-founder	Collaborated with the OS Awards. Eu project members on a joint blog post regarding open source talent investment which was published with Techpolicypress.
FOSS Backstage	March 2026	Event	Facilitated the participation of OS Awards.eu project members to

Organisation	Date	Contact Role	Notes
		organiser	present and speak on open source topics and the Academy activities.
Drupal	March-April 2026	Co-founder	Series of meetings to deliver a blogpost on European digital sovereignty for the EUObserver.
Sovereign Cloud Stack	8 April 2026	Lead SCS Standards	Participated as the speaker during the 4th EOSA webinar
Omnis Cloud	8 April 2026	CEO	Participated as the speaker during the 4 th EOSA webinar
T-systems / Open Telekom Cloud	8 April 2026	CTO	Participated as the speaker during the 4 th EOSA webinar
Capgemini	8 April 2026	VP Global Cloud Lead	Participated as the speaker during the 4th EOSA webinar
Dutch Ministry of Interior	8 April 2026	Open Programme Office	Participated as the speaker during the 4th EOSA webinar
European Tech Map	March-April	CEO	1-on-1 meeting to discuss and work on a joint blogpost about the European Open Source and digital alternatives.

Table 11 Overview of EOSA established synergies by M18

3 Exploitation Plan

3.1 Exploitation Planning

3.1.1 KER 1 (Academy and Awards): European Open Source Academy and Awards Framework

A new institution, EOSA, will be established that will own and take up the Awards Framework and form the basis and sustainability for the annual European Open Source Awards. This KER will include the institution itself, the awards procedure, sustainability mechanisms and the pilot academy members and network. KER 1 Specifically contributes to two project objectives:

- Objective 1: Create a framework for a sustainable recognition scheme for OS in Europe and
- Objective 2: Establish a European OS Awards Ceremony to promote OS contributions.

The specific communication and dissemination objective for this KER was to (1) position the Academy as player in the European OS ecosystem via Campaign 1: Branding & Awareness and (2) Ensure high participation and visibility of awards events via Campaign 3: Flagship Event Promotion & Recruitment.

Result	Contributors	Exploitation Plan and Status	
KR1.1: Critical areas to recognize and metrics for identification of potential nominees and custom awards. D3.1 Manual on the use of OS indicators (KPI1.2.2)	RISE	Exploitation Plan	RISE, APELL, BSC will utilise gathered success stories to support its own advocacies within their own communities.
		Status	Cartography of areas in Open Source Software and Hardware critical to recognise has been compiled, highlighting challenges and policy recommendations for future work.
D4.1 OS Academy Constitution	OFE	Exploitation Plan	Long-Term Institution Building: Develop a legal entity for EU OS Academy to sustain the awards or be sustained further via a funder.
		Status	Done. The Constitution was submitted to the European Commission and will be updated in line with the legal entity. The setup of the Academy is ongoing with different options under consideration. A funding plan for the Academy's long-term financial sustainability has also been established.
KR2.2: Develop a comprehensive awards framework <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D4.2 Awards framework • D5.2 Awards framework 2 	OFE	Exploitation Plan	Explore the annual awards event series being absorbed as part academy activities to support its sustainability. Pursue synergies with Free Open Source Software Developers' European Meeting (FOSDEM) including opportunities for inclusion as part of the programme.
		Status	In progress. The annual awards have been integrated into a broader programme

Result	Contributors	Exploitation Plan and Status	
			branded as “EU Open Source Week” organised in the working days before the FOSDEM weekend in Brussels. This guarantees high-level attendance at the Ceremony as guests are likely to attend more than one event during that week.
KR2.3: Recurrent annual European OS Awards Ceremony <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D4.3 Awards Event framework 1 • D5.3 Awards Event framework 2 • D4.4 Post-event report: Awards Event 1 • D5.4 Post-event report: Awards Event 2 	Trust-IT	Exploitation Plan	The event framework and post-event reports and assets will provide guidance for awards ceremonies after the project concludes. The branding assets, messaging, channels etc. will be handed over to the new academy legal entity at the end of the project duration.
		Status	As the results are being delivered, they are being archived and will be ready to be handed over to the succeeding implementers of the future awards ceremonies at the end of the project.
D5.1 Sustainability plan for the EU Open Source Week initiatives	OFE	Exploitation Plan	Incorporation of the Annual Awards as part of OFE’s annual EU Open Source Week.
		Status	In progress. Both the inaugural ceremony and the 2026 ceremony were hosted on the EU OS Week, with the inaugural ceremony held on the same evening of the Open Source Policy Summit organised by OFE, and the 2026 Awards organised on the evening before.
KR4.1: OSAwards.EU permanent web presence	Trust-IT	Exploitation Plan	Project website revised into Academy website to be the institution’s main online channel.
		Status	Done. Website is now considered as the official online channel of the academy. Trust-IT commits to maintaining the website online at its own cost at least 5 years after the project ends.
KR4.2: Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan & Strategy (DECP) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D7.1 First Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan 1 • D7.2 Intermediate Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan 2 • D8.1 Final Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Report 	Trust-IT, OFE, RISE	Exploitation Plan	The communication plans and assets will provide guidance for future academy communications activities. The branding assets, messaging, channels etc. will be of immediate use to the new academy legal entity even after the end of the project duration.
		Status	There is already a working relationship between the OSAwards comms team and the members of the Academy. Handover of the activities to the succeeding implementers of the communication activities can be easily carried out. Tentatively however, Trust-IT as the main communication partner in OSAwards will maintain the channels and ensure operation until the Academy takes over.

Table 12 KER 1 Exploitation Planning

3.1.2 KER 2 (Skills Strategy): Strategy for OS Skills Development

This KER includes customised training modules aimed at professionals and students, as well as SMEs to close the gap between academic knowledge and real-world industrial application as well as workshops, masterclasses, and industry-led seminars designed as part of the project aiming to increase European proficiency in open source technology.

KER 2 specifically relates to the Project Objective 3: Increase European skills in OS to build a strong workforce. To enable its exploitation, the specific dissemination and communication objective was to demonstrate high interest for the Academy upskilling outputs via Campaign 2: Academy Awareness & Participation.

Result	Contributors	Exploitation Plan and Status	
KR3.1: Formulate Effective OS Exploitation Strategies. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> D6.1 Exploitation & Knowledge Transfer Guidelines 	Tecnalia, BSC, FHG,	Exploitation Plan	Integration of these guidelines as a Code of Practice at the EC Knowledge Valorisation Platform. Fraunhofer ISI supports the uptake through its expertise in innovation systems, technology transfer, and policy-oriented knowledge transfer.
		Status	State of the Art research ongoing regarding OS&HW exploitation strategies and interaction with standardisation. Fraunhofer ISI is contributing perspectives on applied research organisations and public-sector innovation contexts.
KR3.2: Develop Lifelong Learning Programmes and Tailored OS Modules <ul style="list-style-type: none"> D6.2 Skills Strategy and Lifelong Learning Programs Grade & Master Module on OS Hardware & Software Advanced Pre-Doctoral Module on OS/OH 	BSC, Tecnalia, RISE,	Exploitation Plan	Integration of training modules into industry learning programmes, University curriculum, EOSA masterclasses, and partner capacity-building initiatives
		Status	The assessment of training needs for professionals, students, and the academic community has been completed through a survey. A list of existing third-party online courses has been compiled and will be posted on the website. The initial design of the learning programs on operating systems is underway.
KR3.3: Project Sustainability: OS Skills Hub, Endorsement System Feasibility and Continuous Improvement Based on Stakeholder Feedback D6.3 OS Skills Resource Hub and Continuous Improvement (KR3.3)	BSC	Exploitation Plan	Future Academy entity to maintain the European OS Resource Hub. Professional Recognition to explore possibility of an OS endorsement system. BSC to promote courses across its network
		Status	Scoping activities in progress for the Hub architecture, quality assurance model, and continuous improvement framework.

Table 13 KER 2 Exploitation Planning

3.1.3 KER 3 (OS Thought-Leadership): Thought-Leadership Outputs and Tools

This KER includes reports, tools or methodologies produced within the project that are meant for uptake by external stakeholders. This KER will position the Academy as a major resource for best practices, policy suggestions, and strategic advice in the European open-source community.

KER 3 related to Project Objective 4: Increase OS engagement through awareness campaigns and synergies. To enable its exploitation, the specific dissemination and communication objective was to promote OS adoption in public sector, critical industries, and SMEs via multipliers via Campaign 4: Open Source Synergies.

Result	Contributors	Exploitation Plan and Status	
D3.2 OS indicator design and policy recommendations	RISE, FHG	Exploitation Plan	Incorporate OS indicators in DESI, EU Innovation Scoreboard. Fraunhofer ISI to integrate OS indicators in the portfolio of science and technology indicators produced for the German government and EC. Tecnia and BSC to exploit technology transfer opportunities relevant to its own activities.
		Status	Fraunhofer ISI is assessing how OS indicators can be linked to existing STI indicator work, including policy monitoring, benchmarking, and advisory activities related to digital sovereignty and open digital infrastructures.
Policy & Technology Briefs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI1.1.1 Policy recommendations for increased interest for the contribution to, integration of and exploitation of OS assets in Europe • 3 Policy Briefs 	Tecnia, RISE, FHG	Exploitation Plan	Uptake of OS policy recommendations for national OSPOs or EU policymaking. Trust-IT to explore OS Awards.EU opportunities in OS & ICT standardisation for its own standardisation initiatives.
		Status	Initial policy and indicator-related inputs are being developed. Fraunhofer ISI will contribute where relevant to the evidence base and policy framing of OS indicators.
KR1.2 Visualisation tool of OS projects	Tecnia	Exploitation Plan	Incorporate the tool in EOSA webpage to be used by academy members and other potential users. Future Academy entity maintains the Visualisation tool.
		Status	Various dashboards implemented and working other indicators and metrics to be included.

Table 14 KER 3 Exploitation Planning

4. Conclusions

This document outlines the dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities carried out from November 2024 to April 2026 by the OSAwards.eu project. The reported activities reflect updates to the planning strategy aimed at extending the visibility and reach of the European Open Source Academy and European Open Source Awards.

A revamped press engagement strategy delivered higher impact compared to previous periods. The project website saw the launch of new sections (including a dedicated policy section and a preview of the Visualisation Tool, with a full release planned for after Summer 2026), alongside a refreshed homepage, amongst others. Additional webinars and masterclasses were organised, the European Open Source Awards 2026 edition was held, and new synergies were established. The document also presents early exploitation insights and a more detailed roadmap for project results. It is worth noting that the project's overall external communication approach has been progressively refined since M6. As previously mentioned, the European Open-Source Academy and the European Open-Source Awards aspire to be recognised as prestigious European institutions. The initial strategy (which prioritised selectivity in external communications) has since evolved towards greater openness, while still maintaining the formal tone befitting institutions with prestigious mindset. A practical example of this shift is the publication of the European Open Source Awards 2026 agenda, a practice that was not adopted for the 2025 edition, even as the event retained its invitation-only format. Similarly, the frequency of posts across official social media channels has increased, while preserving a consistently institutional voice and tone.

All activities detailed in this report were tracked and measured, providing clear direction for the remaining project months. The next iteration of this document, entitled “D8.1 Final Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Report”, scheduled for delivery in April 2027 (M30), will provide a comprehensive overview of all activities carried out and results achieved by OSAwards.eu. It will place particular emphasis on the exploitation of all identified OSAwards.eu KERs, while presenting a strengthened and consolidated positioning of both the European Open Source Academy and the European Open Source Awards at the European and global levels. This will be underpinned by the timely implementation and continuous refinement of communication and dissemination activities, aligned with evolving sector conditions.

Appendix I. Handbook

The handbook is meant to be a live resource, periodically updated, to provide an easy point of reference for the communication and outreach guidelines and reference plans for the OSAwards.EU consortium. The file is accessible here:

<https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/XLqTqo9t7Pqi3T2>

The current text as of 24 April 2025 can be found below.

Handbook on Communications and Outreach

This document is meant to be a live resource, periodically updated, to provide an easy point of reference for the communication and outreach guidelines and reference plans for the OSAwards.EU consortium.

Last update: 24 April 2026

Regular Calls & Meeting Minutes

- **WP7-8 and Comms Calls:** These occur twice a month, on Thursdays, 11-12:00 CET to align on dissemination, exploitation, and communication efforts.
- Meeting minutes and schedules are documented and accessible here: <https://cloud.apell.info/f/25079>. Partners are encouraged to review them before calls.
- Attendance is expected for at least one representative from each partner organisation: TECNALIA, BSC, APELL and Fraunhofer are accepted to only attend when needed or desired.

Branding & Communication Assets

- **Branding Guidelines:** Follow project-wide branding for consistency across all materials. Access the latest guidelines here: <https://cloud.apell.info/f/29180>
- **Templates & Design Assets:** Download templates for presentations, social media, and official documents here: <https://cloud.apell.info/s/79sNeSj5cn4JDtE>
- **Communication Kit:** Includes design files for rollups, general Academy presentation, flyers, posters, and digital banners. Available here: <https://cloud.apell.info/f/29188>
- **Style guide:** a style guide is being developed to further harmonise the style of communication for EOSA. This file will be shared once a first version has been crystalised.

Event Participation & Support Requests

- **Notifying the Team:** Partners attending conferences, workshops, or industry events should inform the communications team at least **4 weeks in advance or alternatively update the Event tracker:** <https://cloud.apell.info/f/29188>
- **Support Available:** We provide materials, branding advice, and strategic communications support. If needed, partners can request:
 - Co-branded materials (flyers, presentations, etc.).
 - Social media promotion before, during, and after the event.
 - [Press releases](#) or blog posts related to the event.

- **Collaboration Example:** For MWC, we worked with BSC to maximise visibility. Partners should refer to this case for best practices.
- Submit event details via Tracker: <https://cloud.apell.info/f/29188> or email a.radonjic@trust-itservices.com

Sharing News & Updates

- **When to Share:** Partners should inform the communications team about:
 - Submission of key deliverables.
 - Progress on technical developments.
 - Participation in major events or collaborations.
 - Any other newsworthy updates.
- **How to Share:** Provide a short summary (who, what, when, where, why) via **E-Mail to a.radonjic@trust-itservices.com** or email.
- The **Academy events** and news are collected through a form provided by OFE (Nicholas Gates)
- **Amplification:** The team will coordinate dissemination through social media, newsletters, and website updates.

Key Information for Partners

- **Communications Plan (D7.1):** The full dissemination and communication plan is detailed in D7.1. Access it here. <https://cloud.apell.info/f/21308>
- **Communication Plan (D7.2):** in the process of implementation
- **Consistency Across Channels:** Ensure messaging aligns with the overall project strategy and the neutral political stance and tone of the Academy.
- **Social Media & Website Contributions:** Partners can contribute to blog posts, case studies, and social media campaigns. Contact the communications team for guidelines.
- **Contacts & Support:** For any questions, reach out to l.mari@trust-itservices.com and a.radonjic@trust-itservices.com.
- **Press Contact:** For any references and enquires please reach out to: l.mari@trust-itservices.com and r.carrillo@trust-itservices.com

Appendix II. Media Press Clippings

Below are some of the pieces and visuals published on media and social media channels during the second reporting period of the project. These are non-exhaustive, as it's a continuous dialogue with press and external media that are following the project's evolution. A complete list will be provided at the time of last report.

N	Date	Channel	URL	Media Type	Est. Audience
1	20260130	LWN.net	https://lwn.net/Articles/1056699/	Online News (domain)	383k monthly visits
2	20260130	The Bryant Review	https://gardinerbryant.com/interview-with-european-open-source-award-winners-greg-kh-jenny-molloy-and-frank-karlitschek/	Online Blog (domain)	97.6k monthly visits
3	20260130	Gardiner Bryant	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XRTXLkuVOrw	YouTube Channel	100k+ subscribers
4	20260130	International Centre for Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology	https://www.icgeb.org/dr-jenny-molloy-honoured-at-european-open-source-awards/	Institutional Channel	35k monthly visits
5	20260130	Just Linux	http://justlinux.ca/aggregator/sources/4	Online News (aggregator)	1k monthly visits
6	20260201	Linux Mint	https://linuxmint.hu/hir/2026/02/greg-kroah-hartman-kapta-a-2026-os-european-open-source-awards-fodijat	Online News (domain)	50k monthly visits
7	20260201	Linuxiac.com	https://linuxiac.com/european-open-source-awards-2026-honor-greg-kroah-hartman/	Online News (domain)	513k monthly visits
8	20260202	OSTechNix	https://ostechnix.com/greg-kroah-hartman-open-source-award-2026/	Online News (domain)	116k monthly visits
9	20260202	ItsFOSS.com	https://itsfoss.com/news/greg-kroah-hartman-european-open-source-award/	Online News (domain)	1.3 million monthly visits
10	20260205	NextCloud	Nextcloud CEO and founder Frank Karlitschek wins European Open Source Award for Business & Impact	Online News (domain)	1.7M monthly visits

N	Date	Channel	URL	Media Type	Est. Audience
11	20260202	Massa Critica	Premiati gli European Open Source Awards 2026. Premiati Di Cosmo e Zacchiroli per il progetto Software Heritage	Online News (domain)	2k monthly visits
12	20260202	DevOpsChat	Linux's Second-in-Command Greg Kroah-Hartman Bestowed With The European Open Source Award	Online News (domain)	11.8k monthly visits
13	20260202	LXer – Linux News	https://lxer.com/	Online News (aggregator)	52k monthly visits
14	20260112	Orcwg	FOSDEM and EU Open Source Week 2026: Key Events for the ORC Community	Online News (domain)	1.2k monthly visits
15	20260203	Sololinux	Greg Kroah-Hartman recibe el máximo reconocimiento en los Premios Europeos de Código Abierto 2026	Online News (domain)	13k monthly visits
16	20260218	basque press	The international community highlights the value of Open Source	Online News (domain)	752 monthly visits
17	20260204	Tecnalía	https://www.tecnalia.com/noticias/tecnalia-refuerza-compromiso-open-source	Institutional Channel	59.4k monthly visits
18	20260205	Library for Open Science	https://lib-os.ru/novosti/prisuzhdena-premiya-za-vklad-v-otkrytoe-programmnoe-obespechenie/	Online News (domain)	8k monthly visits
19	20260205	Prohoster	https://prohoster.info/en/blog/novosti-interneta/gregu-kroa-hartmanu-prisuzhdena-premiya-za-vklad-v-otkrytoe-po	Institutional Channel	122k monthly visits
20	20260206	Linux Magazin	https://www.linux-magazin.de/news/european-open-source-awards-verliehen/	Online and Print	91.3K monthly visits
21	20260209	Mia mamma usa linux	https://www.miamammausalinux.org/2026/02/leuropean-open-source-academy-assegna-gli-european-open-so...	Online Blog (domain)	20.8k monthly visits
22	20260210	Linux News DE	https://linuxnews.de/european-open-source-awards-vergeben/	Online News (domain)	123.5k monthly visits
23	20260209	GOyou.it	https://www.goyou.it/tecnologia/2026/02/09/european-open-source-awards-2026-riconosciuti-innovatori-e-pionieri.html	Online News (domain)	79 monthly visits
24	20260206	OSSDirectory	https://www.ossdirectory.com/en/topnews/details/verleihung-der-european-open-source-awards-2026	Online News (domain)	5.6k monthly visits

N	Date	Channel	URL	Media Type	Est. Audience
25	20260206	Telecom Paris	https://www.telecom-paris.fr/prix-europeen-open-source-software-heritage	Online News	408.4k monthly visits
26	20260212	Fosstopia DE	https://fosstopia.de/european-open-source-awards-2026/	Online Blog (domain)	23.4k monthly visits
27	20260209	Engineering Biology in Cambridge – Uni of CAmbridge	https://www.engbio.cam.ac.uk/news/engbio-co-chair-dr-jenny-molloy-receives-special-recognition-award	Institutional Channel	4.2K monthly visits
28	20260209	Aggregatore GNU/Linux e dintorni	https://www.laserooffice.it/blog/2026/02/03/pr-emi-europei-per-il-software-open-source-2026-riconoscimento-a-greg-kroah-hartman-per-il-suo-contributo-al-kernel-linux/	Aggregator of news	44k monthly visits
29	20260203	Science Business	https://sciencebusiness.net/news/recognition-open-source-trailblazers	Online News (domain)	150.7k monthly visits
30	20260214	Condividere et Impera	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/abbiamo-bisogno-di-sovrانيت%25C3%25A0-digitale-rudy-bandiera-1htbf/?trackingId=HHTFCF1RT7Wh1Gjz5o4C%25FQ%3D%3D	LinkedIn Newsletter	28,524 subscribers
31	20260205	Open Source initiative	https://opensource.org/blog/open-source-at-the-heart-of-europes-and-the-worlds-digital-future	Institutional Channel	492.3k monthly visits
32	20260217	NGI Commons	https://commons.ngi.eu/2026/02/17/eu-open-source-week-2026-demonstrates-growing-institutional-commitment-to-digital-commons-and-open-technologies/	Institutional Channel	n/A

116k monthly visits

100k channel subscribers

1.3 million monthly visits

35k monthly visits

13k monthly visits

European Open Source Awards 2026 Honor Linux Kernel Maintainer Greg Kroah-Hartman

Linux kernel maintainer Greg Kroah-Hartman has received the top prize at the 2026 European Open Source Awards in Brussels.

513k monthly visits

Premiati gli European Open Source Awards 2026. Premiati Di Cosmo e Zacchiroli per il progetto Software Heritage

2k monthly visits

Greg Kroah-Hartman kapta a 2026-os European Open Source Awards fődíját

50k monthly visits

Progetti open source che stanno rivoluzionando l'intelligenza artificiale in tutto il mondo

197k monthly visits

The Award for Excellence in Open Source goes to Greg Kroah-Hartman

383k monthly visits

Linux's Second-in-Command Greg Kroah-Hartman Bestowed With The European Open Source Award

11.8k monthly visits

The Award for Excellence in Open Source goes to Greg Kroah-Hartman

1k monthly visits

European Open Source Awards 2026 Honor Linux Kernel Maintainer Greg Kroah-Hartman

11.8k monthly visits

59.4K monthly visits

5.1M monthly visits

ENG version

122.6K monthly visits

LINUX News Magazine Podcast Shop

European Open Source Awards verliehen

Von Ulrich Bantle - 06. Februar 2026

Daniel Stenberg und Greg Kroah-Hartman. Quelle: European Open Source Academy

Die European Open Source Academy vergibt die European Open Source Awards jährlich in Brüssel. Der Preis für „Excellence in Open Source“, die höchste Auszeichnung, ging an Greg Kroah-Hartman.

Mit den Awards werden herausragende Leistungen und Einflussnahme im Bereich Open-Source-Software und -Hardware in ganz Europa gewürdigt. Als Träger des Preises für „Excellence in Open Source“, mit der langjährige Führungsqualitäten und Leistungen im Bereich Open Source gewürdigt werden, wurde Greg Kroah-Hartman als einer der weltweit einflussreichsten Softwareentwickler und langjährigen Betreuer des Linux-Betriebssystems geehrt.

MiaMammaUsaLinux.org

Notizie Articoli Meetup

L'European Open Source Academy assegna gli European Open Source Awards e, oltre a Linux, c'è anche molto Italia!

Rosal Scarazzini 9 Febbraio 2026

European Open Source Awards

Il 20 gennaio 2026, a Bruxelles, si è svolta la cerimonia degli **European Open Source Awards**, un evento organizzato dalla **European Open Source Academy** (EOSA) e dal scopo di premiare e riconoscere il lavoro che i contributori open-source svolgono in tutti quei progetti critici per la società nel nostro mondo digitale.

The home of European excellence in Open Source: è così che si definisce l'European Open Source Academy, ed è lavoro che svolge sempre per far fronte a quello che è un problema di cui ci si rende conto quasi sempre quando è troppo tardi: riconoscere l'importanza del lavoro svolto da chi contribuisce all'open-source nei suoi vari ambiti. Non solo quando lo sviluppo non si, ma anche la promozione ed i contributi per il progresso dell'approccio aperto.

<https://www.miamammausalinix.org/2026/02/09/european-open-source-awards-e-oltre-a-linux-ci-è-anche-molto-italia/>

Leading figures from Europe's open source ecosystem have been recognized for their contributions to Europe's digital sovereignty, skills and competitiveness as part of the European Open Source Awards.

By Thomas Bell, Senior Analyst, Analyst@tomahawk.be, @senioranalyst

Photo credit: Trust IT

At the second annual European Open Source Awards, Greg Kroah-Hartman received the main prize in recognition of the "outstanding impact" of open source software development, technical leadership and sustained excellence over several decades.

Greg Kroah-Hartman receiving the award for "outstanding impact" in open source software development. Photo credit: Trust IT

"I feel very privileged and honoured that my peers have recognized the work I have done for so long," Greg Kroah-Hartman, a fellow of the Linux Foundation, told the awards ceremony at the historic Schloss Hezeberg in Salzburg on 20th January. "It's a real joy that there are so many developers doing this work." The global, open source community is a core strength of the open source ecosystem, "making code more readily available and making it work for 20 years is a totally different kind of engineering. The open source community is really good at that. It is the maintaining a bridge for 100 years."

20.8K monthly visits

Science Business
150.7K monthly visits

LN LINUXNEWS

European Open Source Awards in Brüssel vergeben

10. Februar 2026 | Fortschritt | News | Schreibe einen Kommentar

Die **European Open Source Awards** sind ein jährlich stattfindendes europäisches Auszeichnungsprogramm, das herausragende Beiträge zu Open-Source-Software und -Hardware in Europa öffentlich würdigt. Die jetzt zum zweiten Mal vergebenen Auszeichnungen sind Teil der EU-geführten Initiative **OS Awards** und sollen Sichtbarkeit, Anerkennung und Interesse an Open Source in Europa erhöhen sowie deren Nutzung und Verwertung in Europa stärken.

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Bereit für die E-Rechnung?

123.5K monthly visits

Newsroom

Prix européen pour l'initiative Software Heritage

10 février 2026

Lors de la cérémonie des European Open Source Awards 2026, Stefano Zacchiroli, professeur à Telecom Paris, a été distingué, aux côtés de Roberto Di Cosimo, chercheur à l'Université Paris-Saclay, par une Special Recognition for Community engaged pour leur initiative Software Heritage.

Il est heureux de voir un projet de logiciel libre comme Software Heritage être récompensé par un prix européen. Stefano Zacchiroli, professeur à Telecom Paris, a été distingué, aux côtés de Roberto Di Cosimo, chercheur à l'Université Paris-Saclay, par une Special Recognition for Community engaged pour leur initiative Software Heritage.

«Nous sommes honorés de recevoir le prix annuel European Open Source Award au nom de Software Heritage et de son équipe dévouée. C'est une grande reconnaissance et nous sommes fiers de contribuer à la communauté open source et de partager nos expériences et nos connaissances avec les autres membres de la communauté open source.»

408.4K monthly visits

fosstoppia Blog Linux Distributions Online Kurse Podcast Other

European Open Source Awards rücken prägende Persönlichkeiten ins Zentrum

10. Februar 2026

«Wie auch immer...»

Die European Open Source Awards ehren herausragende Persönlichkeiten im Bereich Open Source. Die Auszeichnungen würdigen Menschen und Initiativen, die offene Technologien in Europa vorantreiben.

In Brüssel wurden die Preise für die FOSSAD Awards überreicht. Der Hauptpreis ging an Greg Kroah-Hartman. Er trägt die Verantwortung für den Erfolg von Linux, obwohl er aus den USA stammt, aber er hat sich in den Niederlanden nieder gelassen und ist unverzichtbar für die Linux Community.

Ein weiterer Preisträger ist der Kategorie Business and Impact. Der Hardware-Gründer setzt sich seit Jahren für digitale Souveränität ein. Stefano Zacchiroli erhält die Auszeichnung für Community Impact. Er engagiert sich stark für Software Heritage und die Bewahrung von Qualität.

Die Preise wurden von Matthew Venn für die OS Awards Foundation überreicht.

23.4K monthly visits

Engineering Biology in Cambridge

EngBio co-chair Dr Jenny Molloy receives Special Recognition award

Submitted by r2758 on Mon, 09/02/2026 - 10:01

Dr Jenny Molloy received Special Recognition for Advocacy and Awareness at the 2nd Annual European Open Source Awards, held in Brussels.

The Special Recognition for Advocacy and Awareness award is given to the individuals espousing open source as included in the policy-making agenda, raising the awareness of open source technologies and its community.

Dr Molloy, Group Leader in the Department of Biocatalysis at the University of Cambridge, was recognized for her pioneering leadership in Open Science Hardware, including co-founding and organizing the Gathering of Open Science Hardware at CERN in 2016, which initiated a community that now convenes several hundred members via an online forum and regular events. She has also played a key role in establishing the Open Material Transfer Agreement, a tool that enables open exchange of biological materials, designed to support openness, sharing and innovation in global biotechnology.

Commenting on the award, Dr Molloy said: "I'm delighted to see open hardware for science increasingly recognised internationally over the last decade since I co-founded the Gathering for Open Science Hardware. This

4.2K monthly visits

Abbiamo bisogno di sovranità digitale

February 14, 2025

Il software digitale domina tanto lavoro, specie con quello che sta nascendo in Cina. Come mai allora non fare il software che interessa a noi e a noi stessi?

Da che l'Europa non sia particolarmente bella appare chiaro a tutti, ma per fortuna non è tutto nero. Bisogna fare alcune scelte e metterle in atto, senza tempo di parole, e il "modello dell'open source" è il modello Open Source Europe. Questo non significa, infatti, un semplice abbandono del codice chiuso (dogmatico, insostenibile, antiscientifico, improntato alla parzialità a cui, in realtà, si è sempre e ormai abituati) in favore di un'alternativa basata su principi di collaborazione e trasparenza.

L'open source è un'idea di un software sviluppato al pari di un'opera d'arte o di un'opera di ricerca. Bisogna essere aperti a nuove idee e a nuove collaborazioni. La "Biblioteca Bologna" è un esempio di questo. È un progetto di ricerca che ha coinvolto studenti, ricercatori, docenti e personale. È un progetto che ha coinvolto studenti, ricercatori, docenti e personale. È un progetto che ha coinvolto studenti, ricercatori, docenti e personale.

Il "Modello per l'Open Source" è un progetto che ha coinvolto studenti, ricercatori, docenti e personale. È un progetto che ha coinvolto studenti, ricercatori, docenti e personale. È un progetto che ha coinvolto studenti, ricercatori, docenti e personale.

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February 5, 2026 · Events · OSGE Policy Team

Open Source at the Heart of Europe's (and the World's) Digital Future

Every year, FOSDEM – the Free and Open Source Developers' European Meeting – turns Brussels into a global meeting point for the Free and Open Source software community. In 2026, that energy extended well beyond the university halls, as policymakers, founders, developers, and civil society gathered to confront a shared reality: Open Source is no longer operating at the margins of technology policy. It is foundational to Europe's digital sovereignty, security, and resilience.

From Code & Compliance and the EU Open Source Academy Awards and Policy Summit, to multiple FOSDEM devrooms, the Open Source Initiative (OSI) engaged directly with the community throughout the week, connecting conversations, contributing expertise, and reinforcing the importance of open governance in an increasingly regulated digital landscape.

Turning Regulation into Practice at Code & Compliance

492.3K monthly visits

Interview with European Open Source Award winners Greg KH, Jenny Molloy, and Frank Karlitschek

by Gardner Bryant

Right now in Brussels, Belgium, FOSDEM is happening. But last night the winners of the European Open Source Awards, a new award for Open Source (OS) developers, were celebrated! This was a block to meet where they Academy honored the "open builders" of Europe's digital world. To every business, organization.

The winners included:

- Frank Karlitschek of [Red Hat](#), for Business & Impact
- Jenny Molloy of [Cambridge for Open Science Hardware](#) for Advocacy & Awareness
- Man Tien of [The Linux Foundation](#) for B2B & Advocacy
- Rubens Di Castro and Stefan Zachhold of [Jitsi](#) for Community Impact

And they also awarded Linux Kernel developer Greg KH with the Excellence in Open Source prize!

The folks at the Academy invited me to attend the event but, unfortunately, the session starts in the US so I couldn't get there and made it back in time to report. However, so to be honest, I got in a call with some of the award winners and had a chance to interview them!

Thank you to the European Open Source Academy for putting on this event and highlighting the amazing work that FOSDEM developers do!

A few things to note: the Q&A here is based on a video that I recorded. [The video is on YouTube.](#) The questions and answers here have been lightly edited for clarity.

Now, let's get to the interview!